

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

PLIGHTS AND PREDICAMENTS IN THE PHARMACY INDUSTRY

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 01/11/2017

Available online

06/12/2017

Keywords

Pharmaceutical Industry,
Biosimilars, Policies,
Advertising, Consumer,
Market, Nmes- New
Molecular Entities,
FDA – Food and Drug
Association,
DTCA- Direct-To-Consumer
Advertising,
DPCO- Drug Price
Controlling Order,
OTC- Over the Counter.

ABSTRACT

We provide an insight to the troubles in the field of pharmacy. Using the published literature to date, we review the impact of various challenges in the field of Pharmacy. The pharmaceutical industry has succumbed to the challenges presented by the consumer, other healthcare fields, policies, emergence of telemedicine, sunken research inputs, low drug approval, diminished new drug release in the market, demolishing new drug acceptance and utility. These factors have provided considerable damage to the pharmaceutical industry which can be explicated by the languishing market growth. The consumer aimed advertising meant for profit has the patients educated about branded drugs and also has mislead them to drug abuse. The misled and educated patients have deteriorated the market of generic drugs. The conflict in the marketing of NMEs, Biologics and Biosimilars creates yet another hurdle. The growth of approval of new drugs compared to the year 2016 was just 3% this year. The non-revising policies do not tend to improve the profit of the drug manufacturers but favour the economy of the consumer alone. The industry is spiralling and requires stabilization. We conclude by suggestions by newer reformed policies, better innovations, clear sources of information, thorough pharmacovigilance and well counselled consumers.

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Please cite this article in press as **Neha Naaz et al.** Plights and Predicaments in the Pharmacy Industry. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(11).

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INTRODUCTION

A cell is the basis of any organism is a fact we have known forever but we have failed to acknowledge another fact that the patient is the basis for the Pharmaceutical Industry. The emergence of the pharmaceutical industry, the pharmacy education process, various courses to learn pharmaceutical sciences at various colleges is only for the patients who are the ultimate consumers. Being the centre of origin and the basis of the whole pharmacy system the patient turns the industry to highs and lows and also determines the changes and evolution. This review determines the various factors responsible for the diminishing pharmacy industry.

The evolution of the pharmaceutical industry also depends on the demands and expectations of the patient aka the ultimate consumer. The newly aggravating diseases which are pertinent to the hazardous inventions, super infections and various other factors instigate innovative techniques for healthcare. The invention of various devices, tests, scales for disease study and treatment have remarkably improved leading to the decline in active participation of pharmacists. The pharmacists have merely been viewed as any other retailer and not a healthcare provider.

The healthcare system over decades evolved into a patient centric system with a team of healthcare professionals to improve the quality of life. The upsurge of various diseases and the corresponding pharmacotherapeutic regimens was tremendous until now. The Pharma industry has many obstacles and hurdles and it slows down midway the race of innovation. The challenges it faces from different sectors have ultimately damaged its very base, the patient.

The patient centric growth has led to the growth of the pharmacy field and has also grounded it. The relationship between the healthcare payers and healthcare providers has been inequitable. The patient expects a newer and cost-effective therapy as an alternative to the conventional and standard treatments which can sometimes be expensive. The drawbacks and factors for the slackened industry of pharmaceutical products can be summed up as follows:

OVER EXPECTATIONS OF PATIENTS:

The patient demands are sometimes out of the league and cannot be fulfilled. The pharmaco-economics sure fortify cost-effective regimens but the disease severity in the patient and the financial condition of the patient contradict each other [1]. This challenges the work of a pharmacist at various levels like a clinical pharmacist for the failure of Patient care plan, a hospital pharmacist for the inability to deliver cost-effective drugs and the retailers and manufacturers face a loss and the industrial growth diminishes.

INNOVATION IN OTHER SECTORS

The changing environment has given life to the various inventions which provide ease and information to the patients. The discovery of Telemedicine, Biometric devices, involvement of the digital and information technology led to more educated patients [2]. Though Telemedicine is not exactly a cost-effective means of healthcare [3] it has educated patients to a different level. The simultaneous innovation from pharmaceutical industry was dubious which is another failure in Patient healthcare.

CLINICAL RESEARCH AND TRIALS

The clinical research and trials have led to the discovery of various new molecular entities (NMEs) which can provide a higher level of safety and efficacy or surpass the conventional drugs in the market. The Biologics and Biosimilars are two categories of drugs which have a potent market and also can fabricate the growth and profits of Pharmaceutical Industry.

Biologics like monoclonal Antibodies are used in various sectors. Biosimilars on the other hand are not approved by the FDA. They do not gain market approval due to the expensive Clinical trials they require [4]. The trial is quite exorbitant and the lack of funding of these by the Government has ultimately deteriorated patient care.

Only 2 Biosimilars have been approved of the many which were discovered. A classic example of Biosimilars is the anti-inflammatory drug "Inflectra" which is used in conditions like Psoriasis, Arthritis and other diffused inflammatory conditions [5].

The field of Pharmaceutical research and developments has been steady and the growth has remarkably declined. The lack of newer inputs contributes to the failure of innovation in Pharma failing the needs of the patient.

IMMOBILITY FROM LAB TO MARKET

The process of new drug approval is undoubtedly slow and some drugs do not reach the marketing phase. This phenomenon of immobility of the innovation from the research lab to the market and then to the patient has been contributed by various factors, few being expensive clinical trials, uncertain efficacy, lack of funding, lack of acknowledgement and others. However, the disapproval of new drugs by FDA has also taken turns in diminishing the industry growth by reducing the approval of new drugs to 51% in 2016. There was a slight increase in the approval of new novel drugs in 2017 with 54% approval [6].

GOOD MANUFACTURING PRACTICES

The ideal manufacturing practices set the standards for the best outcomes from industries. Compliance of the manufacturing industries with these has benefits to both the industry and the patient. The conventional management of Industries attributes to the diminishing growth as it is insufficient in the current scenario of astounding innovations from other healthcare fields.

ADVERTISING:

It was not until 1981 the ultimate consumer was aimed by the pharmaceutical industry. The advertisements are arrows of marketing while the bow is value-based. Value based marketing of the products shifts the consumer interests from brand to brand of drugs [7] or change in care plan [8]. The consumers or patients felt more educated or concerned after their Direct-to-Consumer Advertisements (DTCA). These encouraged about 39% patients to initiate a discussion with their prescribers [9]. Despite few advertisements being an aid for awareness among the consumers, many misleading advertisements have produced negative impact on the growth of the pharmaceutical industry [8].

POLICIES

The healthcare policies have brought a change in the healthcare management sector and also in the development of pharmaceutical industry. The healthcare act in the current scenario is steadily maintained alongside the Drugs and cosmetics Act.

The Drug Price Controlling Order (DPCO) is yet another factor which limits the growth of the profit of the Pharmaceutical industries. New Drug Price Controlling Order 2013 aimed to lower the prices of the drugs [3]. It has been concerned with the economy of the patient while being negligent of the Industry profit and thereby diminishing the growth. The pricing of the drugs is limited and thus few drugs do not reach few rural or undeveloped markets as they are not affordable by them.

ACCEPTANCE AND UTILITY

The Indian pharmaceutical market holds a revenue of USD 20 billion where the branded drugs preponderate the entirety with 70%, the generic drugs with 21% and the least is contributed by the OTC medications with 9% [3]. The market of Biosimilars and biologics though requires a higher investment can return a greater revenue to the Indian pharmaceutical companies.

The innovations in the sector are not utilized at the best rates to produce appalling results due to either lack of knowledge of prescriber, low advertising, product specific demerits or the strict guidelines for disease treatment. The post marketing phase of the drugs requires strict monitoring and the inactivity of pharmacists in pharmacovigilance of newly marketed drugs leads to inappropriate feedback and utilization of it.

CONCLUSION

The pharmaceutical industry has evolved simultaneously with the evolution in the other fields of science and has managed to always survive the challenges in the process. The recent advancements in other fields in the past decade have brought various hurdles for the growth of Pharmaceutical industry. The pharmaceutical industry ultimately can be summed as an aid to the patient who primarily dictates the growth and abatement of it either directly or indirectly. The different sectors of Pharmaceutical Industry Management, Clinical research, Drug policies, Healthcare system are the secondary factors which create the margin of profit and loss, growth and decline. The field of pharmacy can grow only when these basic challenges are conquered. Newer regulatory policies are required for consumers with changing life style and requirements. The appreciation and approval for innovations is much required. The process of patient education should be changed to an obligatory process which will help the consumers get the best. The concept of individualized medicine shall be taken to newer levels to improve the healthcare payer and healthcare provider relationship.

List of Abbreviations:

NMEs- New Molecular Entities

FDA – Food and Drug Association

DTCA- Direct-to-Consumer Advertising

DPCO- Drug Price Controlling Order

OTC- Over the Counter

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